

Functional diversity of copepod communities in the north-western Barents Sea

Tiziana Durazzano^{a,*}, Slawomir Kwasniewski^b, Marta Gluchowska^b, Raul Primicerio^a, Janne E. Søreide^c, André W. Visser^d, Haakon Hop^e, Camilla Svensen^a

^a Department of Arctic and Marine Biology, UiT the Arctic University of Norway, 9037 Tromsø, Norway

^b Institute of Oceanology, Polish Academy of Sciences, 81-712 Sopot, Poland

^c The University Centre in Svalbard, 9171 Longyearbyen, Norway

^d VKR Centre for Ocean Life, Technical University of Denmark, 2800 Kongens Lyngby, Denmark

^e Norwegian Polar Institute, Fram Centre, 9296 Tromsø, Norway

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Functional traits
Arctic copepods
Trait-based ecology
Feeding modes
Lipids
Barents Sea
Trade-offs

ABSTRACT

Trait-based approaches offer a powerful alternative to traditional species-centred methods by offering a mechanistic understanding of complex ecosystems. This study investigates the functional diversity of copepod communities in the north-western Barents Sea with a focus on trait distribution, trade-offs, and the influence of local environmental conditions across latitudinal and depth gradients. Despite the ecological importance of copepods, the Arctic remains poorly characterized in these respects. To address this knowledge gap, we analysed the spatial diversity of copepods and identified potential trade-offs among three functional traits: body size, feeding strategy, and lipid content. Using community-weighted means, variances, and Redundancy Analysis, we examined trait-environment relationships across bioregions and depth layers in a shelf area expanding from warmer ice-free waters in the south to colder seasonal ice-covered waters in the north and into the basin. Our findings reveal distinct trait distributions: the region south of the Polar Front in warmer waters, copepods tend to be smaller, lipid-poor and predominantly particle feeders, characteristic of a detritus-based food web with higher trait variability. In contrast, the Arctic Shelf and Arctic Basin regions are dominated by larger, lipid-rich copepods with lower trait variances, reflecting strong environmental filtering. Ambush feeding is the prevalent strategy in surface waters across the transect, whereas cruise feeding and a high proportion of wax esters relative to total lipids are primarily observed in the deeper layers. This research enhances our understanding of the functional complexity of Arctic mesozooplankton communities and provides a baseline for predicting future potential regime shifts.

1. Introduction

Trait-based approaches, which are gaining popularity in aquatic sciences, offer a powerful alternative to traditional species-centred methods by providing a mechanistic understanding of complex ecosystems (Kjørboe et al., 2018). Traits are measurable individual properties of organisms, such as body size, feeding mode, or physiological rates, that influence their performance and interactions with the environment and other species (Violle et al., 2007). The fundamental premise is that the spatio-temporal distribution of organisms and their functional role in ecosystems depend on their traits rather than their taxonomic affiliation (Kjørboe et al., 2018, Litchman et al., 2013).

In ecological community studies, traits help define how organisms interact with their environment and with each other, providing insights into community assembly through ecological niche formation mechanisms (Sodré & Bozelli, 2019, Vogt et al., 2013). Two key mechanisms shaping community structure are environmental filtering and competition. Environmental filtering, which describes the relationship between an organism and its environment (Kraft et al., 2015), is mediated by the traits an organism expresses. This occurs because not all organisms can successfully establish and persist under all abiotic conditions (Kraft et al., 2015). In contrast, competition influences traits in a way that promotes diversity by favouring differences among coexisting organisms by relative fitness differences, which reflect asymmetries in competitive

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: tiziana.durazzano@uit.no (T. Durazzano).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2025.103560>

Received 15 March 2025; Received in revised form 16 July 2025; Accepted 25 August 2025

Available online 26 August 2025

0079-6611/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

abilities that can lead to competitive exclusion. However, a species may persist alongside a competitor if it possesses traits that provide a competitive advantage or reduce niche overlap (Chesson, 2000). Trait-based ecology emphasizes the pivotal role of functional traits in structuring communities and shaping ecosystem properties (De Bello et al., 2010).

Central to this framework are empirical trade-offs, defined as measurable compromises where a species' investment in one trait or function reduces its capacity in another, directly influencing feeding, survival and reproduction (Litchman et al., 2013). Organisms face inherent trade-offs, as they cannot optimize all functions simultaneously due to physiological constraints (Kjørboe, 2024). This energy allocation influences favoured strategies and can trigger cascading ecological effects (Kjørboe, 2011). These trade-offs are critical drivers of biodiversity patterns, as they determine how species partition resources, colonize habitats, and compete across spatial scales (Kjørboe et al., 2018).

Copepods, the most abundant group of marine zooplankton, are vital components of the Arctic pelagic ecosystem (Wold et al., 2023). The functional and taxonomic diversity of these small crustaceans is high (Benedetti et al., 2016), and they represent the key link within pelagic food webs, serving as the main pathway of energy transfer from primary producers to fish (Wassmann et al., 2006) and contributing significantly to key important ecosystem processes such as the biological pump (Darnis et al., 2024, Gawinski et al., 2024, Iversen, 2023, Oliveira et al., 2022). While global studies on zooplankton traits and functional groups have already been conducted (Benedetti et al., 2023, Ward et al., 2012), the Arctic remains poorly characterized. To date, no in-depth investigations into the functional traits and associated trade-offs of copepod communities in the Barents Sea have been carried out, despite extensive research on copepod taxonomy. The scarcity of trait data for the Arctic species, coupled with the region's complex hydrography and connectivity with the Atlantic, has made functional trait characterization challenging.

Among the functional traits of copepods, body size is considered a master trait, playing an important role in organismal physiology, including metabolism and growth, and is closely linked to population dynamics through predator–prey relationships (Andersen et al., 2016). Feeding modes play a critical role in determining species ecological interactions due to their ecological implications beyond feeding (Kenitz et al., 2017, Mariani et al., 2013). Each feeding mode influences patterns such as predation risk and mating interactions, as the trophic strategy is determined by the resource acquisition mechanism (Visser & Fiksen, 2013). The efficiencies of various feeding modes are balanced against their metabolic costs, with certain modes being more successful in specific environments (Kjørboe, 2011). Thus, feeding mode is considered a critical trait, as dietary preferences may shift with food availability (McGinty et al., 2018). Other traits, such as lipid content, are equally critical in Arctic ecosystems. Lipid content in copepods plays an important ecological and biogeochemical role in energy storage and transfer, and in carbon export through processes such as the lipid pump (Jónasdóttir et al., 2022, Record et al., 2018, Visser et al., 2020). Understanding the distribution of these traits provides insights into how copepods adapt to environmental gradients and contribute to ecosystem functioning.

The Barents Sea, with an average depth of 230 m, is a commercially important fishing area (Nakken, 1998). Changes in zooplankton availability influence the trophic web, with possible repercussions to fisheries (Pedersen et al., 2021). As short-lived ectotherms whose metabolism and development depend on abiotic factors, copepods are vulnerable to environmental changes (Richardson, 2008). Regime shifts in copepod communities are already occurring, with notable consequences for ecosystem functioning. In a regime shift documented in the North Sea, a decline in copepod nutritional quality was observed, along with a potential mismatch between fish larvae and the peak availability of their prey, driven by a transition to detritivore-dominated communities (Deschamps et al., 2023).

Recently, the Barents Sea has been warming at more than twice the rate of the rest of the Arctic during winter (Cai et al., 2022), accompanied by “Atlantification”—a process in which warm Atlantic water is increasingly advected into the high-latitude ocean (Gerland et al., 2023, Ingvaldsen et al., 2021, Polyakov et al., 2023). Observations indicate a decline in sea-ice extent and concentration (Chen et al., 2016, Screen & Simmonds, 2010), along with the emergence of new pathways for Atlantic water inflow into the Barents Sea (Kalhagen et al., 2024). Given the pivotal role of zooplankton in channelling energy within the ecosystem and their significant contribution to the carbon cycle (Ramondenc et al., 2023), the anticipated impacts of climate change are of great concern. Particularly, changes in life strategies of main community members could affect the efficiency and strength of the biological carbon pump via biological processes such as ingestion (sloppy feeding), growth (incorporation of new matter into body tissue), reproduction (production of eggs and consequently offspring), egestion (repackaging ingested matter into faecal pellets) and respiration (Oliveira et al., 2022, Pinti et al., 2023, Sodre & Bozelli, 2019).

Variations in zooplankton biomass, influenced by predation from planktivorous fish and the transport dynamics via the Atlantic inflow, highlight the interconnected effects of climate change on zooplankton dynamics and fisheries (Dalpadado et al., 2024, Olsen et al., 2024). To effectively predict and mitigate future regime shifts, it is essential to first characterize the current ecosystem.

By understanding the distribution of copepod functional traits, associated trade-offs and their relationship with environmental gradients, we can establish a baseline to detect functional regime shifts as they occur. However, the specific variations in copepod functional traits and their correlations with the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the water masses remain unknown, partially due to complex and dynamic hydrography in the Barents Sea. The area studied here includes diverse pelagic environments in the north-western Barents Sea, providing a unique opportunity to explore functional traits across varying gradients of bathymetry, water masses, and seasonality. Within this framework, this study investigated the following research questions: 1) which functional traits characterize Arctic copepod communities, and how are they spatially distributed; 2) are there any trade-offs that emerge among regions; and 3) how does the environment influence these patterns?

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

Material for this study was collected during five surveys aboard the R/V *Kronprins Haakon* as part of the Nansen Legacy project. The sampling design covered four seasons with the summer and late autumn surveys (Q3 and Q4) performed from 5 to 27 August 2019 and 28 November – 17 December 2019, while late winter, spring, and summer surveys (Q1, Q2 and JC2-1) were carried out from 2 to 25 March 2021, 27 April – 20 May 2021 and 12 July – 29 July 2021. The transect covered seven stations, stretching from the central Barents Sea (76°N) across the shelf break and into the Arctic Ocean (82°N), thus capturing a complex environmental gradient from Atlantic to Arctic waters (Fig. 1).

The Barents Sea serves as a critical conduit for the inflow of warm, saline Atlantic Water (AW) into the Arctic Ocean, playing a vital role in water mass transformation and dense-water production that supports the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation (Kolas et al., 2024a). This high-latitude region is characterized by distinct ecosystem structures and ecological dynamics, which are heavily influenced by water-mass properties and seasonal variations. The polar front divides the Barents Sea into two distinct zones: the northern Arctic region, dominated by cold, low-salinity Arctic water entering from the northeast and typically ice-covered during winter, and the southern subarctic region, which remains largely ice-free due to the influx of warm, saline, and

Fig. 1. Sampling stations (red dots) for the seasonal survey in 2021. The current system, including the NAC (Norwegian Atlantic Current), NoCC (North Cape Current), WSC (West Spitzbergen Current), and the main paths of polar surface waters and ice-drift, is depicted by colored arrows (Figure modified from Wold et al., 2023).

nutrient-rich Atlantic water (Barton et al., 2018, Kolås et al., 2024b, Oziel et al., 2016).

2.2. Copepod abundance data

Copepods were sampled using duplicate depth-stratified tows with nets of mesh sizes 64 μm and 180 μm (MultiNet type Midi – Hydro-Bios, opening: 0.25 m²). This sampling strategy targets a wider size range, including smaller size copepods (calanoids, e.g. *Microcalanus*, cyclopoids, e.g. *Oithona* and harpacticoids, e.g. *Microsetella*). Individuals were counted and identified to species level whenever possible, including gender and developmental stage, following the method in (Postel L,

2000) with modifications. Details of the laboratory zooplankton sample examination procedure can be found in (Wold et al., 2023) and references therein. Data on copepod abundance (ind. m⁻³) in each sampled depth layer from the different sampling campaigns are available in Wold et al., 2023. In this study, the abundances obtained individually from the two mesh sizes were combined, with abundance data for small taxa and stages derived from the 64 μm net and abundances on larger taxa and stages from the 180 μm net samples, following procedures described by Wold et al., 2023.

Copepods were sampled at fixed depth intervals, with slight adjustments made at the deepest stations. At the shallow shelf stations (P1–P5), the sampled depths ranged from the seafloor (approximately

300 m, though this varied slightly between stations) to 200 m. This range is labelled as '300–200 m' in the plot and data. The sampling also included the depth intervals 200–100 m, 100–50 m, 50–20 m, and 20–0 m. At the shelf break and deep station (P6 and P7), the intervals were 600–200 m, 200–50 m, 50–20 m, and 20–0 m. For analytical purposes, each depth interval at each station was treated as a single data point, resulting in a total of 154 data points. Since species composition varies by depth, time and location, each datapoint was assumed to represent a distinct copepod community as a group of copepod species with varying compositions and/or abundances co-occurring within each depth layer at a specific time.

For the analysis of functional traits, only abundances of adult females and males, as well as copepodid stages V and IV, were used, as these stages represent the majority of each species' biomass (Supplementary Fig. 1), as well as since evidence supporting similarities of qualitative traits among early copepodite stages is dubious. The total number of copepod species in the dataset was 32, reflecting the taxonomic pool of species along the transect. However, the abundances of three species from the genus *Paraeuchaeta*, two from the genus *Pseudocalanus*, and two from *Spinocalanus* were combined due to a lack of data on functional traits at the species level. Furthermore, the species *Aetideopsis rostrata*, *Centropages hamatus*, *Jaschnovia brevis* and *Triconia conifera* were excluded from the analyses as they occurred only once in the dataset. This resulted in 19 copepod species available for analyses of functional traits.

2.3. Functional traits selection and literature search

We selected functional traits of copepods based on categories established by Brun et al., 2016 and Benedetti et al., 2016, with values derived from adult females. To better reflect Arctic life histories, particularly for continuous traits, values were sourced from the available literature and updated when Arctic and sub-Arctic data became available. Literature searches were conducted using Web of Science and Google Scholar, employing Boolean combinations in the topic field tag to identify reliable trait measurements for the selected species. Keywords and common synonyms were used to enhance the search yield. The search spanned all databases (Web of Science Core Collection, Grants Index, KCI, Preprint Citation Index, and ProQuest™) and covered an all-year timespan. Results were manually screened for eligibility, and values measured in the Barents Sea were prioritized when available.

In the present study, we assigned each trait value measured for adult females to abundance data encompassing copepodite stages CIV–CVI. This approach was adopted due to the difficulty in finding records of continuous traits for specific life stages. Additionally, most trait-based research focuses on adult female features, which are often applied to counts of different life stages as well as biomass, as adult females are considered the population's endpoint (Benedetti et al., 2016, Benedetti et al., 2018, Benedetti et al., 2023, McGinty et al., 2018, Pomerleau et al., 2015, Venello et al., 2021, Zheng et al., 2023). While copepods have complex life cycles that may exhibit unique traits at different stages (Brun et al., 2017), the lack of available data often necessitated this approach. In cases where specific trait data were unavailable for a species, the category "NA" (Not Assigned) was used.

Functional trait categories were selected given their relevance to the Arctic marine ecosystem. The selected traits, which are detailed in

Supplementary Table 1, include body size (continuous variable), feeding mode (fuzzy-coded variable), lipid content (continuous variable), and wax ester content (continuous variable). These traits were chosen to target morphological characteristics and life-history strategies related to Arctic conditions. The feeding modes are based on the classification provided by Kiørboe, 2011 and by Brun et al., 2016. In summary, current feeders create a flow to filter large volumes of water, capturing non-motile prey that is individually detected. Cruise feeders actively swim to intentionally encounter motile prey. Ambush feeders use a "sit and wait" strategy, remotely detecting motile prey before making contact and attacking. Particle feeders are aggregate-colonizing copepods associated with the consumption of large non-motile particles, such as marine snow, by feeding on their component parts (Koski et al., 2021). Feeding modes were coded as a fuzzy variable, allowing species to be assigned to multiple categories by representing the trait in multiple columns. This approach provides flexibility to partially account for potential plasticity in the feeding behavior of certain copepod species. Lipid content was included to better capture the different life-history strategies associated with lipid reserves. Total lipid content was expressed as the percentage of lipids relative to dry mass, while wax ester content was expressed as the percentage of wax esters relative to total lipids. These values were derived from adult females to ensure consistency across species. Lipid traits are particularly relevant in Arctic ecosystems, where copepods rely on lipid reserves to survive extreme seasonal variations in food availability (Lee, 1975).

2.4. Environmental variables and defining the bioregions

A shipboard conductivity, temperature, and depth profiler (Seabird 911plus CTD), attached to a 24-bottle rosette system, was deployed at all sampling stations. To ensure reliable data when the CTD was deployed from the ship's moonpool (which could introduce uncertainty in the measurements), temperature and salinity values were interpolated to a default depth of 13 m, following the method described by Koenig et al., 2024. The mixed layer depth was defined as the depth in meters where the potential density exceeds the surface potential density by 0.03 kg m⁻³ (De Boyer Montégut et al., 2004), and it was calculated using the R package *castr* version 0.1.0 (Irissou, 2023). Values of potential temperature (°C), practical salinity (PSU), potential density anomaly (σ_T), photosynthetic radiation (mol m⁻² s⁻¹), volume fraction of oxygen in seawater (mL L⁻¹) and mass concentration of Chlorophyll *a* (mg m⁻³) were measured *in situ*. The sea-ice thickness (m) was obtained from satellite data generated using E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information (CMEMS). The data has a daily resolution and a spatial resolution of 6 km, and the information for the specific sampling day at each station was extracted with the use of the Free and Open Source QGIS software. We used the definitions by (Sundfjord et al., 2020) for water mass classification based on the potential temperature (°C), practical salinity (PSU) and potential density anomaly (σ_T) that were converted using the package *gsw* version 1.1–1 (Kelley et al., 2024). The values were averaged for each of the depth layers sampled with the Multinet, except for the Chlorophyll- α mass concentration, which was averaged for the upper 50 m. To identify possible underlying patterns in the environmental data, we employed Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using the *ade4* package version 1.7.22 (Dray S, 2007) on scaled data (Supplementary Fig. 1). This preliminary analysis, combined with previous

Table 1

Summary of p-values from pairwise comparisons for significant traits across three different bioregions in the NW Barents Sea using the Wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction for log-transformed Community Weighted Mean (CWM). The p-values are adjusted using the Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) method. Significant results are marked as follows: * ($p < 0.05$), ** ($p < 0.01$), *** ($p < 0.001$).

Region Comparison	Body Size	Total Lipids (%DM)	Wax Esters (%TL)	Current Feeding	Cruise Feeding	Particle Feeding
Arctic Basin vs Arctic Shelf	0.63	<0.001***	0.031*	0.859	0.005**	0.487
Arctic Basin vs south of the Polar Front	<0.001***	0.19	<0.001***	0.002**	0.019*	0.013*
Arctic Shelf vs south of the Polar Front	<0.001***	<0.001***	<0.001***	0.002**	0.453	0.011*

oceanographic knowledge from Koenig et al., 2024 and Wold et al., 2023, allowed us to group the stations into distinct bioregions based on their hydrography and bathymetry.

The southernmost station (P1), located south of the polar front, was consistently influenced by Atlantic Water (AW; $T > 2.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $S \geq 1035.06\text{ kg m}^{-3}$) and modified Atlantic Waters (mAW; $0.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} < T \leq 2.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $S \geq 1035.06\text{ kg m}^{-3}$) throughout all seasons, entering the Barents Sea from the southwest. Due to this constant inflow, P1 is categorized as the “south of the Polar Front” group (Fig. 2).

In contrast, stations P2-P5 experienced stratified Polar Waters (PW; $T < 0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $S \leq 1027.97\text{ kg m}^{-3}$) within the first 100 m, occasionally extending down to 200 m, across all seasons. These waters originated from the Nansen Basin and were influenced by local sea-ice interactions. Below this layer, Intermediate Water (IW; $-1.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} < T \leq 0.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $S > 1027.97\text{ kg m}^{-3}$) or warm Polar Water (wPW; $T > 0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $S < 1035.06\text{ kg m}^{-3}$) predominated based on seasonal inputs of modified AW that was advected onto the shelf (Lundesgaard et al., 2022). These stations are collectively referred to as the “Arctic Shelf” group. Further north, stations P6 and P7, located at the northern shelf break and in the deep Nansen Basin, respectively, featured Polar Water in the surface layer

(0–200 m) and a core of AW or mAW at intermediate depths (200–400 m). These stations are classified under the “Arctic Basin” group, in connection with the advection of warmer, saltier Atlantic-origin waters into the Barents Sea. This transport originated from the West Spitsbergen Current (WSC), which flows from the northwest into the P6 and P7 locations (Fig. 1).

2.5. Comparing functional traits among bioregions and trade-offs

The distribution patterns of the functional traits were analysed by calculating community-weighted means (CWM) and complemented with community-weighted variance (CWV) as a measure of their spread for the different bioregions. Community-weighted mean quantifies the average value of a trait selected to characterise a community, weighted by the abundance of each species showing this feature or trait. By contrast, community-weighted variance measures the variance of a trait within a community, weighted by the abundance of each species constituting the community. CWMs provide a measure of the diversity of a functional trait within the community, reflecting how it varies. We used it as a proxy for the community’s ability to withstand increased

Fig. 2. Distribution of water masses across stations and seasons. Water masses are classified according to Sundfjord et al. (2020). AW = Atlantic Water, mAW = modified Atlantic Water, PW = Polar Water, wPW = warm Polar Water, AIW = Arctic Intermediate Water.

variability in the environment, as well as to identify areas of significant abiotic filtering, advected species income, competitive niche displacement, and/or temporal variation (Maitner et al., 2023). High trait variance usually corresponds with high functional redundancy, ensuring the relative independence of community functions from species turnover over space and/or time (Frainer et al., 2021). The community-weighted means of trait values were determined for each data point using the BAT package version 2.9.6 (Carvalho, 2024) for untransformed abundance data and considering all 19 copepod species. Community weighted variance was calculated on untransformed abundance data, based on Frainer et al., 2021 and the code available at https://github.com/andre-frainer/Functional_Variance/blob/main/cwv.R/. The community-weighted means and the community-weighted variances were log-transformed to stabilize variance and improve normality. We further statistically compared values of the two measures among the different bioregions in the epipelagic layer (0–200 m) to test for consistent patterns of variation according to the environmental and bathymetrical constraints. For this analysis, only data from this depth range were selected to ensure comparability along the transect. Considering that most copepods stayed in the upper 100 m of the water column with minor differences among years and seasons (Gawinski et al., 2024), we considered the data from 0–200 m as representative of the epipelagic environment. However, we acknowledge that traits below 200 m are also relevant and are discussed in the manuscript where appropriate to provide a broader context for depth-related patterns in trait distribution, despite not being statistically tested. Statistical assumptions for normality and homogeneity of variances were evaluated using the Shapiro-Wilk and Levene's tests, respectively. Given the violation of the normality and homogeneity assumptions, the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis Rank test was chosen to pinpoint differences among the three bioregions. Significant results from this test led to subsequent pairwise comparisons using the Wilcoxon test to check for specific differences between groups with continuity correction (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995), controlling the false discovery rate (the expected proportion of false discoveries amongst the rejected hypotheses). The 5 % level was accepted as being statistically significant. The dominant feeding mode was selected for plotting for each depth layer along the transect by identifying the highest community-weighted mean value among the four feeding modes, using log-transformed data. We will refer to empirical trade-offs as the emergence of dominant functional traits in the different bioregions compared to each other. In this context, a trade-off reflects the balance organisms must strike between competing demands on their functional traits, shaped by environmental conditions and ecological interactions. Environmental filtering, which in this case is a result of environmental constraints, drives these trade-offs by favouring traits that enable organisms to tolerate specific abiotic conditions or ecological challenges in each bioregion. For example, in one bioregion traits that prioritize resource acquisition, such as current feeding, and retention, such as higher lipid accumulation, may be dominant while in another bioregion traits that prioritize a less efficient search for prey, such as cruise feeding, and long-term storage of the energy as in higher wax esters ratio to total lipids may be prioritized. These trade-assemblages emerge spatially because of the environmental filtering. Despite this, by examining the dominant functional traits across bioregions, we can infer how environmental filtering and ecological interactions shape community structure and how trade-offs can be shaped in response to varying environmental contexts.

2.6. Statistical analysis linking functional traits to environmental gradients

For assessing the copepod community responses to the environmental gradients in terms of (functional) trait structure, a community-weighted redundancy analysis (CWM-RDA) was performed. CWM-RDA is a constrained ordination method that examines how functional traits, expressed as community-weighted means (CWMs), relate to

environmental variables across ecological communities (Kleyer et al., 2012, Legendre et al., 2011) by combining trait aggregation with multivariate regression. Environmental data were scaled and centred, while community-weighted means underwent a logarithmic transformation to lower skewness and improve normality. Subsequently, the relationships between the environmental variables and the log-transformed community-weighted means were analysed using redundancy analysis (RDA) (Kleyer et al., 2012) using vegan package version 2.6.4 (Oksanen et al., 2022). We used the community-weighted means as the response matrix and the environmental variables as predictors. We conducted a restricted-permutation design appropriate for line transect, using the different seasons as the blocking factor and executed a total of 199 permutations. Restricted permutations are those constrained by prescribed structures, such as avoiding subsequences ordered in specific ways. In this case, the design accounts for the structure of the data, ensuring that permutations respect the seasonal blocks and the line transect. All analyses were performed using R Statistical Software, version 4.3.1 (Development Core Team, 2023).

3. Results

3.1. Spatial variance of key functional traits and trade-offs

We examined the spatial distribution of three key functional traits, body size, feeding modes and lipid content, under the selective pressure of environmental factors and species interactions across a transect featuring a complex oceanic milieu. While seasonal variation is inherently embedded in the data structure, we highlight and discuss seasonal differences in the results only when notable.

3.1.1. Body size

In general, larger copepods were more commonly found in communities inhabiting colder water masses, while smaller copepods were more frequent and numerous in warmer water masses, particularly at the southern location. Three stations, P4, P6 and P7, exhibited a distinct pattern regarding copepod body size. Larger copepods dominated below 200 m at shelf station P4 in March and May, at station P7 on the surface during December, and at depth at station P6 in July. Communities dominated by smaller copepods were more prevalent in March, coinciding with the onset of the new production period, and at depths below 200 m in the Arctic Basin in August, December, March and May (Fig. 3a).

The community-weighted variance of body size was low at the P1 station, particularly during March and May, and was higher in correspondence with higher CWM.

3.1.2. Feeding modes

To gain a better overview, Fig. 4 summarizes the dominant feeding modes along the transect, while detailed patterns can be found in Supplementary Fig. 2.

Along the transect, current feeders exhibited a primarily patchy distribution across seasons, though they were less present in December. Current feeding copepods were most dominant in July and August south of the Polar Front and in the Arctic Basin, with occasional prevalence at station P4 during other seasons on the Arctic Shelf. Particle feeders are mostly represented at station P1, south of the Polar Front, during December and May, but were also present closer to the bottom at stations P2, P4 and P5 in May. They were virtually absent in the Arctic Basin. Cruise feeders were primarily found at the deep station P7 below 200 m, where they persisted year-round. They also had seasonal and spatially patchy distribution below 200 m at P6, P3 and P1 in May.

As indicated by the community-weighted variance scores (Supplementary Fig. 3), the variability of the feeding current trait was generally high, except at P1 in March and May and at depth in December in P3. Community-weighted variances for cruise feeding were generally low along the transect, with exceptions in August at P3, December at P1, March at P4 and July at P6 at depth. Particle feeding variances were

Fig. 3. The distribution of copepod body sizes at the seven transect stations in NW Barents Sea, a) based on log-transformed Community Weighted Mean (CWM) along the transect and b) based on log-transformed Community Weighted Variance (CWV).

high at P1 in December, March and May, highlighting that particle feeding is particularly widespread seasonally.

3.1.3. Lipids

Lipid content, expressed as a percentage of dry weight, was always high on the Arctic Shelf, particularly in the 0–100 m layer and increased in the Arctic Basin stations, particularly in December and March at depth (Fig. 5a).

Meanwhile, the proportion of wax esters, expressed as the percentage of total lipids in individual copepods, increased at greater depths, particularly below 200 m depth (Fig. 5b). The community-weighted variance (Supplementary Fig. 4) for total lipid was generally high, with the only exception at station P2 down to 50 m in March.

3.2. Comparison among bioregions: Key community trade-offs

To assess the significance of the trait patterns across the three bioregions, a Kruskal-Wallis Rank sum test on the log-transformed community weighted means for the upper 200 m was performed (Supplementary Table 2). Statistically significant differences were found for all studied traits, except for ambush feeding. When comparing different bioregions against significant traits (Table 1), the region south

of the Polar Front exhibited highly significant differences for most traits compared to the two other bioregions, indicating a distinct separation in survival strategies between Arctic and Atlantic copepod communities.

The differences between the Arctic Shelf and the south of the Polar Front bioregions were particularly pronounced, with significant differences observed for all traits except cruise feeding. In contrast, the bioregions Arctic Shelf and Arctic Basin were more similar, with no significant differences in traits such as body size, feeding current, or particle feeding. But significant differences were found in lipid content and cruise feeding, with the latter appearing to be associated with greater depths, a habitat absent on the Arctic Shelf. It is worth noting that, in general, the Arctic Shelf showed a higher total lipid content compared to the other two regions, indicating variations in lipid storage strategies for this bioregion.

The analysis of community-weighted variance (CWV) complemented the findings from the community-weighted mean (CWM) analysis, offering additional insights into the functional diversity of copepod communities across the bioregions. In the upper 200 m (Supplementary Table 3), CWV revealed significant differences for most traits, except for wax-esters and ambush feeding. Pairwise comparisons (Supplementary Table 4) further highlighted significant differences between bioregions, particularly between the Arctic regions (Arctic Shelf and Basin) and the

Fig. 4. Dominant feeding modes observed along the transect stations in NW Barents Sea. This figure summarizes the key trends in feeding mode distributions, while detailed patterns across stations, depths, and seasons are provided in Supplementary Fig. 2.

south of the Polar Front. These patterns were consistent with the results from the CWM analysis illustrated above.

3.3. Environmental variables shaping the distribution of copepod functional traits

The RDA analysis revealed that a depth gradient delineates a primary axis of trait variation (RDA1), affecting trophic strategies and lipid accumulation (Fig. 6a). This underscores the critical role of depth as a key environmental driver in the spatial distribution of functional traits.

Points on the figure that cluster together in the left part of the graph represent the zooplankton communities inhabiting close to the bottom depths on the Arctic Shelf and in the mesopelagic layer of the deeper stations, while points clustering on the right represent communities inhabiting the surface and epipelagic layer. Cruise feeding was predominantly represented in communities at greater depths. In contrast, ambush feeding showed a negative correlation with depth, suggesting a predominance of this trait in shallower, near-surface layers. A horizontal gradient from south to north was distinguishable along RDA2 (Fig. 6b), with samples from depth layers from the southern polar front grouped at the lower part of the graph, while those from the Arctic Shelf and the Arctic Basin overlapped in the centre. Traits negatively associated with RDA2 included body size and wax-ester content, suggesting a decrease in copepod size and wax-ester ratio from the colder ice-covered stations in the northern bioregions to the ice-free well-mixed station in the southern bioregion. The depth of the mixed layer was highly correlated with RDA2, indicating a gradient from highly mixed to highly stratified waters. Temperature and density also emerged as key environmental

drivers shaping the observed trait distributions, with warmer, denser water masses suggested as characteristic environmental conditions for particle feeding copepods. On one hand, current-feeding larger-sized copepods were found well correlated with highly stratified and colder waters, typically present on the Arctic Shelf as well as in the colder Arctic Basin. The particle feeding trait showed positive correlations with temperature and density, indicating a higher prevalence of this type of copepod in warmer, denser and generally well-mixed water masses of possible Atlantic origin. The first two RDA axes explained a substantial portion of the variance, with RDA1 accounting for 25.51 % and RDA2 contributing 13.62 %, confirming the potential role of studied ecological gradients in functional trait distribution across the studied bioregions (Supplementary Table 5).

4. Discussion

In this study, we examined how three key ecological traits relevant to ecosystem function were distributed in copepod communities along a transect crossing a complex ocean environment, such as the polar front zone, as well as across different depth layers. Our goal was to better understand the factors that determine the presence of specific traits and to explore the trade-offs that may shape patterns of trait diversity. Our research approach identified certain general trends. We found that the studied traits are not uniformly represented across copepod communities, with their distribution shaped by environmental factors, with a particular role of water mass types and sea ice. We also noted a significant role of depth-related factors that contributed to the observed trait distribution, reflecting the dynamic nature of ecological niches and food

Fig. 5. The distribution of copepod lipids at the seven transect stations in NW Barents Sea, a) Total lipid as a percentage of individual dry mass based on Community Weighted Mean (CWM) along the transect and b) Wax esters as a percentage of individual total lipids along the transect based on Community Weighted Means (CWM).

availability across depths. Copepod communities found in warmer and well-mixed water masses show a predominance of smaller detritivores such as *Microsetella norvegica*, *Triconia borealis*, and *Oncaea* spp. The communities dominant on the Arctic Shelf are composed of predominantly large and lipid-rich species, exemplified by *Calanus* spp., which are also typically current feeders. Finally, the communities constituting the Arctic Basin group showed distributional continuity with the adjacent Arctic Shelf region in the upper 200 m, but had a different, specific trait composition pattern for communities living at mesopelagic depths, for example, having a noticeably higher proportion of the cruise feeding species. Notably, the traits observed in this study reflect the strong influence of water mass properties and circulation patterns, as well as seasonal environmental change. It must be noted, however, that ontogeny was not accounted for in the analysis due to the exclusion of CI to CIII stages, which could influence the expression of certain traits at finer temporal scales.

4.1. A holistic view of the trait-environment relationships and trade-offs in the Barents Sea

The contrasting water masses and environmental conditions at the Atlantic-influenced and Arctic stations had a significant impact on the

predominance of certain functional traits, leading to niche differentiation. Sea ice coverage and mixing processes in the water column, particularly along the latitudinal gradient of the transect, shaped three distinct bioregions in opposite ways from north to south. These opposing influences highlight the transition from ice-covered, stratified Arctic waters in the north to ice-free, well-mixed Atlantic waters in the south. As ecosystem structure emerges from the environmental filtering – the interactions between individuals and their environment – different traits were favoured in different bioregions, resulting in diverse life-history strategies. Moreover, the three-dimensional nature of the water column plays a crucial role in determining food availability and driving adaptations to food scarcity, predation and light limitation by depth, imposing additional constraints. The interplay between these factors and various functional traits significantly influenced trade-offs, shaping the community niche (Fig. 7).

Ambush feeding showed no significant differences among areas, reflecting a robust feeding strategy across different bioregions. These findings align with previous modelling of feeding behaviours, suggesting that ambush feeding might be a widespread strategy at higher latitudes (Prowe et al., 2019). In contrast, in the permanently Atlantic-influenced southern region, we observed dominance of traits such as particle feeding, which is consistent with warmer, more mixed waters and

Fig. 6. Relationship between copepod functional traits and environmental variables in NW Barents Sea. Triplots display the RDA of community-weighted means and environmental factors associated with trait distributions ($n = 154$). The blue arrows represent the factor group (CWM of functional traits), and the red arrows represent the predictor group (environmental variables). In a) points represent sampling sites and are coloured according to their depth layer (Surface = 0–20 m; Epipelagic = 20–200 m; Bottom Shelf: 200–300 m; Mesopelagic: 200–600 m) while in b) are coloured according to the three bioregions (P1 = south of the Polar Front; P2–P5 = Arctic Shelf and P6–P7 = Arctic Basin). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

suggests a more detritus-regenerated food web, particularly during December to May. This region was also characterized by smaller body sizes and overall lower individual lipid content. These findings align with previous research showing that open and oligotrophic waters generally host smaller individuals (Vilgrain et al., 2021). Additionally, body size and lipid content in the southern region exhibited higher community-weighted variance compared to the Arctic Shelf and the Arctic Basin, suggesting a broader range of body size adaptations, possibly driven by the advection of boreal species (Wassmann et al., 2015), including pulses of *Calanus finmarchicus*, *Microsetella norvegica* and other Atlantic species. Warmer waters favour smaller copepods since they minimize metabolic costs (Karlsson & Søreide, 2024) and reduce predation risks (Langbehn et al., 2023, Langbehn & Varpe, 2017). Particle feeding was the dominating feeding trait at P1, due to the high and spatially restricted presence of *Microsetella norvegica*, and other particle feeding copepods. This pattern may be attributed to a wider range of particulate food sources that are available year-round at this station. Studies on secondary production in the same area highlight an increased presence of ciliates in the Atlantic-influenced side of the Barents Sea, reinforcing evidence of a more detritus-based food web with an enhanced microbial loop (Gawinski et al., 2024). Also, the concurrent presence of smaller copepods with lower lipid accumulation could reflect the environmental selection for an income breeding strategy, where individuals allocate available resources to reproduction directly (Varpe et al., 2009). Copepods within this strategy generally favour smaller sizes due to the food availability that comes with no costs of carrying energy storages, which results in less lipids at a community level (Sainmont et al., 2014). As previously noticed, income breeders tend to dominate more temperate waters (Sainmont et al., 2014), suggesting an environmental filtering, modulated by food availability year-round, that makes this strategy viable in less seasonal areas. Given the pronounced differences in this area compared to the other two bioregions, and considering that the Barents Sea's ecological transition is influenced by the variable inflow of Atlantic water (Polyakov et al., 2023, Sakshaug et al., 2009), the polar front emerges as one of the most important meso- and large-scale oceanographic features in the region (Våge et al., 2014), shaping distinct strategies among copepod communities. This crucial boundary separates the boreal regime highlighted

here from more Arctic-dominated waters (Barton et al., 2018, Kolås et al., 2024b, Oziel et al., 2016, Polyakov et al., 2023) and plays a vital role in shaping biological productivity (Dalpadado et al., 2012, Gawinski et al., 2024).

On the Arctic Shelf, the dominant traits were current feeding and larger body sizes, likely driven by the need to optimize energy management in colder, stratified waters. Current feeding is particularly advantageous in low-turbulence, stratified waters, as it allows copepods to efficiently capture suspended particles with minimal energy expenditure (Bundy & Vanderploeg, 2002). Larger body sizes, on the other hand, may provide greater space for energy reserves and improved swimming efficiency, further supporting survival in energetically demanding conditions (Lee et al., 2006, Morris et al., 1985). This trade-off highlights the ecological strategies employed by copepods to adapt to the unique challenges of colder, stratified Arctic waters. Lipid content was the highest in this region, especially in the upper 200 m. The pattern has not previously been documented in Arctic water masses but has been previously suggested (Karlsson & Søreide, 2024). Furthermore, previous studies have reported a prevalence of larger-sized groups poleward (Benedetti et al., 2023, San Martin et al., 2006, Tang et al., 2022). These findings are consistent with Bergmann's rule, which states that members of the same clade tend to be larger in colder environments (Bergmann, 1847). The application of Bergmann's rule to copepods is generally accepted (Campbell et al., 2021, Daufresne et al., 2009), though the extent to which temperature drives this relationship remains debated, as several other factors may influence this pattern (Berge et al., 2012). These results of larger sizes and higher lipid contents in Arctic waters point to the adoption of a capital breeding strategy, where copepods grow bigger and accumulate reserves during the feeding season to be able to spawn during the winter before the next feeding season (Varpe et al., 2009). The larger sizes and generally higher lipid reserves indicated for this bioregion are consistent with the concept of highly restricted, seasonally regulated food input (Sainmont et al., 2014). The high community-weighted variance scores for body size at specific stations and in specific periods on the Arctic Shelf may indicate episodic variations, likely driven by environmental changes or the advection of larger Arctic species such as *Calanus hyperboreus*.

The Arctic Basin was predominantly characterized by the presence of

Fig. 7. Conceptual chart illustrating the distribution of functional traits in the studied north-western Barents Sea ecosystem across various environmental gradients. The top section represents the latitudinal gradient, while the left side depicts the depth-related gradient. Associated environmental variables are shown at the bottom, and the transect stations are indicated in the upper frame. Within the triangle-shaped trait symbols, plus and minus signs denote the direction of variation. A rectangular bar with a tilde (~) signifies that there is no clear trend.

current feeders and a notably low abundance of particle feeders, particularly in the upper 200 m. The observed distribution of current feeders at deeper layers and ambush feeders near the surface may be explained by differences in prey availability, environmental conditions, and vertical migration behaviour. At greater depths, turbulence is typically lower, and prey is more evenly distributed in the water column. Current feeders are well-adapted to such conditions, as they can efficiently filter suspended particles with minimal energy expenditure. Additionally, many current feeders exhibit vertical migration, moving between deeper layers and the surface to optimize feeding and avoid predation. Larger body sizes, often associated with current feeders, provide the swimming capacity needed to pass through the mixing layer during vertical migration, an ability that smaller organisms, such as typically ambush feeders, may lack. In contrast, near the surface, turbulence and prey density are often higher, favouring ambush feeders that rely on sudden, energy-efficient strikes to capture prey. This distribution reflects a trade-off between feeding efficiency, energy conservation, and vertical migration capabilities, with current feeders optimizing energy use in stable, low-turbulence environments and ambush feeders taking advantage of higher prey densities in dynamic surface waters. Traits such as body size, lipid content, and current feeding in the Arctic Basin closely resembled those observed on the Arctic Shelf. Despite some copepods being adapted to deep-water environments, their relatively low abundance does not significantly influence the overall trait profiles in the upper 200 m. This is supported by

the similar variances in these traits as compared to those on the Arctic Shelf, suggesting a continuum of functional traits extending from the neighbouring bioregion. However, in the mesopelagic layer (200–600 m), cruise feeders were notably more abundant and exhibited a higher proportion of their individual total lipids as wax esters. This highlights the specialized adaptations of deeper-dwelling species to stable, deep-water strata, where food scarcity makes elevated wax ester reserves essential for survival.

4.2. Possible implications for ecosystem processes

4.2.1. Carbon fluxes

The varying trait compositions and ecological strategies observed across the study area may influence the size of the particulate matter, its degradation in the water column, as well as its physical-chemical characteristics and morphotypes, with consequences for the quantity and composition of marine snow (Bodur et al., 2023, Trudnowska et al., 2021). In the Atlantic-influenced regions, where deeper mixed layers and higher biological productivity favour particle feeders, an enhanced recycling of carbon from consumption may reduce POC export efficiency (Koski et al., 2017). In contrast, in the Arctic zones, characterized by the presence of sea-ice, an important component in mediating the sympagic-pelagic-benthic coupling (Niemi et al., 2024), includes the prevalence of larger-bodied species of copepods in the pelagic and, to a lesser extent, ambush-feeding strategies. A substantial presence of larger copepods

producing large, fast-sinking faecal pellets contributes to increasing the POC flux to the seafloor and therefore fuelling pelagic-benthic coupling and carbon export (Darnis et al., 2024). Given that the marine environment is expected to undergo significant changes over the next century due to anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions (Barton et al., 2013), and sea-ice free areas are expected to increase (Dalpadado et al., 2020), it is essential to monitor shifts in copepod functional traits. Changes favouring a more dynamic and detritus-based food web as seen in the area south of the Polar Front may lead to weaker pelagic-benthic coupling in the high Arctic (Amargant-Arumí et al., 2024, Niemi et al., 2024), with consequences for carbon export, cycling and ecosystem functioning.

4.2.2. Mesozooplankton lipidscape

Marine lipids play essential ecological and biogeochemical roles in energy storage, transfer, and downward carbon flux (Record et al., 2018). The lipid pump drives carbon transfer from the ocean surface to deeper waters via lipids in overwintering, vertically migrating zooplankton (Jónasdóttir et al., 2015). The evolutionary significance of lipid storage in marine zooplankton is linked to reproduction, survival during periods of low food availability, predation avoidance, and vertical migration (Scott et al., 2000). There are four principal types of storage lipids in marine zooplankton: triacylglycerols, wax esters, phospholipids, and diacylglycerol ethers (Lee et al., 2006). Wax esters serve as long-term energy reserves for extended fasting periods, while triacylglycerols are metabolized more rapidly (Sargent, 1978). High-Arctic calanoid copepods, such as the current-feeding species *Calanus glacialis* and *C. hyperboreus*, accumulate high total lipid levels and possess larger body sizes (Jónasdóttir et al., 2019, Kattner & Hagen, 2009, Lee, 1974, Scott et al., 2000). These copepods typically undergo diapause, a period of dormancy that allows them to survive adverse conditions by relying on their substantial lipid reserves (Kvile et al., 2019). In this context, wax esters function as long-term energy reserves and serve as an adaptation to the highly seasonal energy input from phytoplankton, which is intense but short-lived (Sargent, 1978). Even smaller species in polar environments exhibit a higher proportion of wax esters relative to their total lipids despite accumulating relatively fewer lipids individually (Kattner et al., 2003). Some species of the genus *Oithona* and *Oncaea* can accumulate substantial wax ester reserves relative to their total lipid content (Kattner et al., 2003, Lischka & Hagen, 2007). This is likely because smaller copepods tend to reproduce year-round (Barth-Jensen et al., 2022, Koski et al., 2021). In general, lipid accumulation patterns appear closely aligned with distinct reproductive and survival strategies (Falk-Petersen et al., 2009). However, to our knowledge, no studies have fully examined the vertical distribution of lipids and lipid classes within the polar water column at a community level (Schmid et al., 2018). Our results suggest that copepods favouring deeper waters tend to have a high proportion of wax esters, reflecting lipid accumulation as a key strategy for surviving periods of food scarcity. Despite their relatively low abundance in deep waters, lipid respiration by these copepods contributes to long-term oceanic carbon storage (Cavallo & Peck, 2020). These findings are in accordance with a concept of interspecific differences in lipid content between shallow- and deep-dwelling species from tropical and subtropical latitudes (Cavallo & Peck, 2020).

4.3. Limitations

Our study provides valuable insights into the functional traits of copepod communities in the Barents Sea, but some limitations should be mentioned. Firstly, our sampling spans two different years, excluding 2020 due to the Covid-19 pandemic. In our analysis, we treat these data points as independent; however, this approach may not fully capture interannual variability or potential long-term trends in copepod community structure and functionality. Secondly, our analysis distinguishes between three bioregions, but the “south of the Polar Front” bioregion

encompasses a single station. Since we consider all vertical layers of this station as independent data points, we believe the study conclusions to be generally robust. However, a note of caution is warranted when interpreting results from the “south of the Polar Front” bioregion. Finally, our study does not include younger life stages of copepods due to the lack of detailed trait information and lower taxonomic resolution at these stages, which makes species-level identification more challenging. Although later developmental stages (CIV to adult) constitute most of the biomass, the exclusion of earlier stages (CI to CIII) may obscure important aspects of community dynamics and ecological functions. Additionally, studies of functional traits typically rely on data derived from adult copepods. Despite this approach being justified, as adults represent the endpoint of the life cycle and are crucial for understanding community traits, it may not fully capture the variability and ecological strategies exhibited across different life stages. For example, while lipid content relative to dry body weight and the wax ester-to-total lipid ratio is commonly measured in adult females, these values can vary significantly across developmental stages, female reproductive status and breeding strategies (Falk-Petersen et al., 2009, Sainmont et al., 2014). Previous research has shown that the three dominant calanoid species tend to have higher wax ester content at the CV stage, suggesting that our results may not fully reflect lipid dynamics throughout the copepod life cycle (Falk-Petersen et al., 2009). Furthermore, although our study focuses on Arctic and sub-Arctic regions, in some cases, trait values were unavailable for these specific regions. Consequently, data had to be sourced from studies conducted in other areas, including the North Atlantic, the Pacific, and the Southern Ocean, with occasional references from tropical regions. This underscores the need for more studies reporting trait data specifically from northern ecosystems. These limitations highlight the need for further research incorporating a broader range of life stages and a more comprehensive characterization of copepod traits, particularly feeding behaviours and lipid accumulation, with documentation of data provenance and extended temporal sampling. In this respect, imaging analysis will be useful to answer these questions in the future (Maps et al., 2024). Such efforts will enhance our understanding of copepod functional ecology and its implications for the Barents Sea ecosystem.

5. Conclusions

Our findings highlight the spatial functional diversity of copepods in the Barents Sea and associated trade-offs, which appear to be influenced by local environmental conditions, particularly by the presence of different water masses and the polar front. In the region “south of the Polar Front”, we observed a dominance of particle feeders, which aligns with warm, stratified waters and suggests a detritus-based food web. This area was also characterized by smaller body sizes and lower lipid content, with high community-weighted variance indicating a diverse range of body size adaptations. On the contrary, the Arctic Shelf and Basin, with their colder, less mixed waters, showed adaptations such as larger body size and higher lipid content, although with lower trait diversity, likely due to strong environmental filtering. Particularly, the Arctic Basin, especially at deeper depths, shows specific adaptations like higher wax ester content, which is essential for survival in harsh polar conditions. Linking functional traits to environmental parameters is crucial for a deeper understanding of the complexity of Arctic zooplankton communities and their role in modulating carbon fluxes and lipidscape. Our study reinforces the significance of body size and feeding strategies in shaping copepod communities’ structure and highlights the pivotal functional role of lipids in the Arctic ecosystem.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tiziana Durazzano: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Slawomir Kwasniewski:** Writing – review

& editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Marta Gluchowska:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Raul Primicerio:** Validation, Supervision, Methodology. **Janne E. Søreide:** Validation, Supervision, Methodology. **André W. Visser:** Validation, Supervision, Methodology. **Haakon Hop:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Camilla Svensen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Funding

This work was funded by the Research Council of Norway through the project The Nansen Legacy (RCN #276730) and in part through the Horizon 2020 project ECOTIP (grant no. 869383) and through the HO-RIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01–3 project POMP (grant nr. 101136875). The position of SK and MG was supported by grant no. 2017/25/B/NZ8/01100 (Tax4Fun) from the National Science Centre, Poland.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Anette Wold for sharing preliminary data and methodology for merging counts from different mesh-sized nets and insights from her previous work, Martin Lindegren and Laurene Pecuchet for continuous support on ecological methods and discussions over the results. We thank the reviewers for their constructive and helpful comments, which have significantly improved the quality and clarity of our manuscript.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocan.2025.103560>.

Data availability

Mesozooplankton biodiversity Nansen Legacy Q3: <https://data.npolar.no/dataset/f7fd75bc-34d2-4a09-ae90-d27286fcb038>, DOI 10.21334/npolar.2022.f7fd75bc Mesozooplankton biodiversity Nansen Legacy Q4: <https://data.npolar.no/dataset/97de88ef-3e5e-47de-93ed-5d8f6883c53a>, DOI 10.21334/npolar.2022.97de88ef Mesozooplankton biodiversity Nansen Legacy Q1: <https://data.npolar.no/dataset/914b8de1-13be-428a-befb-bce6f6f26624>, DOI: 10.21334/npolar.2022.914b8de1 Mesozooplankton biodiversity Nansen Legacy Q2: <https://data.npolar.no/dataset/33385ab0-3e2e-4903-9a50-5be2925e3444>, DOI:10.21334/npolar.2022.33385ab0 Mesozooplankton biodiversity Nansen Legacy JC2-1: <https://data.npolar.no/dataset/bb4e2203-bd73-45a1-a861-89b42d1d0d22>, DOI: 10.21334/npolar.2022.bb4e2203. The CTD data used in this study is available at the Norwegian Marine Data Centre NMDC (<https://nmdc.no>): Nansen Legacy Q3: <https://doi.org/10.21335/NMDC-1107597377> Nansen Legacy Q4: <https://doi.org/10.21335/NMDC-301551919> Nansen Legacy Q1: <https://doi.org/10.21335/NMDC-1491279668> Nansen Legacy Q2: <https://doi.org/10.21335/NMDC-515075317> Nansen Legacy JC2-1: <https://doi.org/10.21335/NMDC-2085836005>.

References

Amargant-Arumí, M., Müller, O., Bodur, Y.V., Ntinou, I.-V., Vonnahme, T., Assmy, P., Kohlbach, D., Chierici, M., Jones, E., Olsen, L.M., 2024. Interannual differences in sea ice regime in the north-western Barents Sea cause major changes in summer pelagic production and export mechanisms. *Progress in Oceanography* 220, 103178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocan.2023.103178>.

Andersen, K.H., Berge, T., Gonçalves, R.J., Hartvig, M., Heuschele, J., Hylander, S., Jacobsen, N.S., Lindemann, C., Martens, E.A., Neuheimer, A.B., Olsson, K., Palacz, A., Prowe, A.E.F., Sainmont, J., Traving, S.J., Visser, A.W., Wadhwa, N., Kjørboe, T., 2016. Characteristic Sizes of Life in the Oceans, from Bacteria to Whales. *Annual Review of Marine Science* 8, 217–241. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-122414-034144>.

Barth-Jensen, C., Daase, M., Ormańczyk, M.R., Varpe, Ø., Kwaśniewski, S., Svensen, C., 2022. High abundances of small copepods early developmental stages and nauplii strengthen the perception of a non-dormant Arctic winter. *Polar Biology* 45, 675–690. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00300-022-03025-4>.

Barton, A.D., Pershing, A.J., Litchman, E., Record, N.R., Edwards, K.F., Finkel, Z.V., Kjørboe, T., Ward, B.A., 2013. The biogeography of marine plankton traits. *Ecology Letters* 16, 522–534. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12063>.

Barton, B.I., Lenn, Y.-D., Lique, C., 2018. Observed Atlantification of the Barents Sea causes the Polar Front to limit the expansion of winter sea ice. *Journal of Physical Oceanography* 48, 1849–1866. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-18-0003.1>.

Benedetti, F., Gasparini, S., Ayata, S.-D., 2016. Identifying copepod functional groups from species functional traits. *Journal of Plankton Research* 38, 159–166. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbv096>.

Benedetti, F., Vogt, M., Righetti, D., Guilhaumon, F., Ayata, S.-D., 2018. Do functional groups of planktonic copepods differ in their ecological niches? *Journal of Biogeography* 45, 604–616. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.13166>.

Benedetti, F., Wydler, J., Vogt, M., 2023. Copepod functional traits and groups show divergent biogeographies in the global ocean. *Journal of Biogeography* 50, 8–22. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.14512>.

Benjamini, Y., Hochberg, Y., 1995. Controlling the False Discovery Rate: A Practical and Powerful Approach to Multiple Testing. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B (Methodological)* 57, 289–300. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2517-6161.1995.tb02031.x>.

Arctic Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast. E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information (CMEMS). Marine Data Store (MDS). doi:10.48670/moi-00001.

Berge, J., Gabrielsen, T.M., Moline, M., Renaud, P.E., 2012. Evolution of the Arctic Calanus complex: an Arctic marine avocado? *Journal of Plankton Research* 34, 191–195. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbr103>.

Bergmann, C., 1848. *Ueber die Verhältnisse der Wärmeökonomie der Thiere zu ihrer Grösse*. Vandenhoeck und Ruprecht.

Bodur, Y.V., Renaud, P.E., Goraguer, L., Amargant-Arumí, M., Assmy, P., Dąbrowska, A. M., Marquardt, M., Renner, A.H., Tatarek, A., Reigstad, M., 2023. Seasonal patterns of vertical flux in the northwestern Barents Sea under Atlantic Water influence and sea-ice decline. *Progress in Oceanography* 219, 103132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocan.2023.103132>.

Brun, P., Payne, M. R. and Kjørboe, T. (2016) A trait database for marine copepods, supplement to: Brun, Philipp; Payne, Mark R; Kjørboe, Thomas (2017): A trait database for marine copepods. *Earth System Science Data*, 9(1), 99–113. PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science. doi: 10.5194/essd-9-99-2017.

Brun, P., Payne, M.R., Kjørboe, T., 2017. A trait database for marine copepods. *Earth System Science Data* 9, 99–113. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-9-99-2017>.

Bundy, M.H., Vanderploeg, H.A., 2002. Detection and capture of inert particles by calanoid copepods: the role of the feeding current. *Journal of plankton research* 24, 215–223. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/24.3.215>.

Cai, Z., You, Q., Chen, H.W., Zhang, R., Chen, D., Chen, J., Kang, S., Cohen, J., 2022. Amplified wintertime Barents Sea warming linked to intensified Barents oscillation. *Environmental Research Letters* 17, 044068. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac5bb3>.

Campbell, M.D., Schoeman, D.S., Venables, W., Abu-Alhija, R., Batten, S.D., Chiba, S., Coman, F., Davies, C.H., Edwards, M., Eriksen, R.S., Everett, J.D., Fukai, Y., Fukuchi, M., Esquivel Garrote, O., Hosie, G., Huggett, J.A., Johns, D.G., Kitchener, J. A., Koubbi, P., Mcennulty, F.R., Muxagata, E., Ostle, C., Robinson, K.V., Slotwinski, A., Swadling, K.M., Takahashi, K.T., Tonks, M., Uribe-Palomino, J., Verheye, H.M., Wilson, W.H., Worship, M.M., Yamaguchi, A., Zhang, W., Richardson, A.J., 2021. Testing Bergmann's rule in marine copepods. *Ecography* 44, 1283–1295. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.05545>.

Carvalho, P. C. S. M. F. R. J. (2024) BAT: Biodiversity Assessment Tools, R package version 2.9.6 ed.

Cavallo, A., Peck, L.S., 2020. Lipid storage patterns in marine copepods: environmental, ecological, and intrinsic drivers. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 77, 1589–1601. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsaa070>.

Chen, H.W., Alley, R.B., Zhang, F., 2016. Interannual Arctic sea ice variability and associated winter weather patterns: A regional perspective for 1979–2014. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 121, 14433–14455. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JD024769>.

Chesson, P., 2000. Mechanisms of Maintenance of Species Diversity. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics* 31, 343–366. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ecolsys.31.1.343>.

Dalpadado, P., Arrigo, K.R., Van Dijken, G.L., Skjoldal, H.R., Bagoien, E., Dolgov, A.V., Prokopchuk, I.P., Sperfeld, E., 2020. Climate effects on temporal and spatial dynamics of phytoplankton and zooplankton in the Barents Sea. *Progress in Oceanography* 185, 102320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocan.2024.103302>.

Dalpadado, P., Ingvaldsen, R.B., Stige, L.C., Bogstad, B., Knutsen, T., Ottersen, G., Ellertsen, B., 2012. Climate effects on Barents Sea ecosystem dynamics. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 69, 1303–1316. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/iss063>.

Dalpadado, P., Prokopchuk, I.P., Bogstad, B., Skaret, G., Ingvaldsen, R.B., Dolgov, A.V., Boyko, A.S., Rey, A., Ono, K., Bagoien, E., 2024. Zooplankton link climate to capelin and polar cod in the Barents Sea. *Progress in Oceanography* 226, 103302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocan.2024.103302>.

- Darnis, G., Geoffroy, M., Daase, M., Lalande, C., Søreide, J.E., Leu, E., Renaud, P.E., Berge, J., 2024. Zooplankton fecal pellet flux drives the biological carbon pump during the winter-spring transition in a high-Arctic system. *Limnology and Oceanography*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.12588>.
- Daufresne, M., Lengfellner, K., Sommer, U., 2009. Global warming benefits the small in aquatic ecosystems. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 106, 12788–12793. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0902080106>.
- De Bello, F., Lavorel, S., Díaz, S., Harrington, R., Cornelissen, J.H., Bardgett, R.D., Berg, M.P., Cipriotti, P., Feld, C.K., Hering, D., 2010. Towards an assessment of multiple ecosystem processes and services via functional traits. *Biodiversity and Conservation* 19, 2873–2893. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-010-9850-9>.
- De Boyer Montégut, C., Madec, G., Fischer, A.S., Lazar, A., Iudicone, D., 2004. Mixed layer depth over the global ocean: An examination of profile data and a profile-based climatology. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 109. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004JC002378>.
- Deschamps, M.M., Boersma, M., Meunier, C.L., Kirstein, I.V., Wiltshire, K.H., Di pane, J., 2023. Major shift in the copepod functional community of the southern North Sea and potential environmental drivers. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 81, 540–552. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsad160>.
- Development Core Team, R., 2023. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Dray, S., D. a., 2007. The ade4 Package: Implementing the Duality Diagram for Ecologists. 22. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v022.i04>.
- Falk-Petersen, S., Mayzaud, P., Kattner, G., Sargent, J.R., 2009. Lipids and life strategy of Arctic Calanus. *Marine Biology Research* 5, 18–39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17451000802512267>.
- Frainer, A., Primicerio, R., Dolgov, A., Fossheim, M., Johannesen, E., Lind, S., Aschan, M., 2021. Increased functional diversity warns of ecological transition in the Arctic. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 288, 20210054. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2021.0054>.
- Gawinski, C., Daase, M., Primicerio, R., Amargant-Arumí, M., Müller, O., Wold, A., Ormańczyk, M.R., Kwasiński, S., Svensen, C., 2024. Response of the copepod community to interannual differences in sea-ice cover and water masses in the northern Barents Sea. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 11, 1308542. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2024.1308542>.
- Gerland, S., Ingvaldsen, R.B., Reigstad, M., Sundfjord, A., Bogstad, B., Chierici, M., Hop, H., Renaud, P.E., Smedsrud, L.H., Stige, L.C., Arthun, M., Berge, J., Bluhm, B. A., Borgå, K., Bratbak, G., Divine, D.V., Eldevik, T., Eriksen, E., Fer, I., Fransson, A., Gradinger, R., Granskog, M.A., Haug, T., Husum, K., Johnsen, G., Jonassen, M.O., Jørgensen, L.L., Kristiansen, S., Larsen, A., Lien, V.S., Lind, S., Lindstrom, U., Mauritzen, C., Melsom, A., Mernild, S.H., Müller, M., Nilsen, F., Primicerio, R., Søreide, J.E., Van Der Meer, G.I., Wassmann, P., 2023. Still Arctic? The changing Barents Sea. *Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene* 11. <https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.2022.00088>.
- Ingvaldsen, R.B., Assmann, K.M., Primicerio, R., Fossheim, M., Polyakov, I.V., Dolgov, A. V., 2021. Physical manifestations and ecological implications of Arctic Atlantification. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment* 2, 874–889. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-021-00228-x>.
- Irisson, J.O., 2023. castr: Process CTD Casts. Version 0.1.0 ed. <https://github.com/jih-o/castr>.
- Iversen, M.H., 2023. Carbon Export in the Ocean: A Biologist's Perspective. *Annual Review of Marine Science* 15, 357–381. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-032122-035153>.
- Jónasdóttir, S.H., Naustvoll, L., Tegllus, F.W., Agersted, M.D., Grenwald, J.C., Melle, W., Nielsen, T.G., Dolgov, A., 2022. Calanus finmarchicus basin scale life history traits and role in community carbon turnover during spring. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 79, 785–802. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsac013>.
- Jónasdóttir, S.H., Visser, A.W., Richardson, K., Heath, M.R., 2015. Seasonal copepod lipid pump promotes carbon sequestration in the deep North Atlantic. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 112, 12122–12126. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1512110112>.
- Jónasdóttir, S.H., Wilson, R.J., Gislason, A., Heath, M.R., 2019. Lipid content in overwintering Calanus finmarchicus across the Subpolar Eastern North Atlantic Ocean. *Limnology and Oceanography* 64, 2029–2043. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.11167>.
- Kalhagen, K., Skogseth, R., Baumann, T.M., Falck, E., Fer, I., 2024. An emerging pathway of Atlantic Water to the Barents Sea through the Svalbard Archipelago: drivers and variability. *Ocean Science* 20, 981–1001. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-20-981-2024>.
- Karlsson, K., Søreide, J.E., 2024. Exploring the role of body mass in temperature-driven changes in metabolic rates of Arctic copepods. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsae188>.
- Kattner, G., Albers, C., Graeve, M., Schnack-Schiel, S., 2003. Fatty acid and alcohol composition of the small polar copepods, *Oithona* and *Oncaea*: indication on feeding modes. *Polar Biology* 26, 666–671. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00300-003-0540-x>.
- Kattner, G., Hagen, W., 2009. Lipids in marine copepods: latitudinal characteristics and perspective to global warming. *Lipids in aquatic ecosystems*. Springer 257–280. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-89366-2_11.
- Kelley, D., Richards, C., 2024. gsw: Gibbs Sea Water Functions. R package version 1.2.0. <http://teos-10.github.io/GSW-R/>.
- Kenitz, K.M., Visser, A.W., Mariani, P., Andersen, K.H., 2017. Seasonal succession in zooplankton feeding traits reveals trophic trait coupling. *Limnology and Oceanography* 62, 1184–1197. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.10494>.
- Kjørboe, T., 2011. How zooplankton feed: Mechanisms, traits and trade-offs. *Biological Reviews* 86, 311–339. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-185X.2010.00148.x>.
- Kjørboe, T., 2024. Organismal trade-offs and the pace of planktonic life. *Biological Reviews* 99, 1992–2002. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.13108>.
- Kjørboe, T., Visser, A., Andersen, K.H., 2018. A trait-based approach to ocean ecology. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 75, 1849–1863. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsy090>.
- Kleyer, M., Dray, S., Bello, F., Lepš, J., Pakeman, R.J., Strauss, B., Thuiller, W., Lavorel, S., 2012. Assessing species and community functional responses to environmental gradients: which multivariate methods? *Journal of Vegetation Science* 23, 805–821. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1654-1103.2012.01402.x>.
- Koenig, Z., Muilwijk, M., Sandven, H., Lundesgaard, Ø., Assmy, P., Lind, S., Assmann, K. M., Chierici, M., Fransson, A., Gerland, S., 2024. From winter to late summer in the northwestern Barents Sea shelf: Impacts of seasonal progression of sea ice and upper ocean on nutrient and phytoplankton dynamics. *Progress in Oceanography* 220, 103174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2023.103174>.
- Kolås, E.H., Baumann, T.M., Skogseth, R., Koenig, Z., Fer, I., 2024. Circulation and hydrography in the northwestern Barents Sea: insights from recent observations and historical data (1950–2022). *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 129, e2023JC020211. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023JC020211>.
- Kolås, E.H., Fer, I., Baumann, T.M., 2024. The Polar Front in the northwestern Barents Sea: structure, variability and mixing. *Ocean Science* 20, 895–916. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-20-895-2024>.
- Koski, M., Boutorh, J., De La Rocha, C., 2017. Feeding on dispersed vs. aggregated particles: the effect of zooplankton feeding behavior on vertical flux. *PLoS One* 12, e0177958. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0177958>.
- Koski, M., Swalethorp, R., Kjellerup, S., Nielsen, T.G., 2021. Aggregate-colonizing copepods in a glacial fjord: Population dynamics, vertical distribution and allometric scaling of growth and mortality rates of *Microsetella norvegica* and *Oncaea* spp. *Progress in Oceanography* 197, 102670. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2021.102670>.
- Kraft, N.J.B., Adler, P.B., Godoy, O., James, E.C., Fuller, S., Levine, J.M., 2015. Community assembly, coexistence and the environmental filtering metaphor. *Functional Ecology* 29, 592–599. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.12345>.
- Langbehn, T.J., Aarflot, J.M., Freer, J.J., Varpe, Ø., 2023. Visual predation risk and spatial distributions of large Arctic copepods along gradients of sea ice and bottom depth. *Limnology and Oceanography*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.12354>.
- Langbehn, T.J., Varpe, Ø., 2017. Sea-ice loss boosts visual search: fish foraging and changing pelagic interactions in polar oceans. *Glob Chang Biol* 23, 5318–5330. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13797>.
- Lee, R., 1974. Lipid composition of the copepod *Calanus hyperboreus* from the Arctic Ocean. Changes with depth and season. *Marine Biology* 26, 313–318. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00391515>.
- Lee, R.F., 1975. Lipids of Arctic zooplankton. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part B: Comparative Biochemistry* 51, 263–266. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-0491\(75\)90003-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-0491(75)90003-6).
- Lee, R.F., Hagen, W., Kattner, G., 2006. Lipid storage in marine zooplankton. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 307, 273–306. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps307273>.
- Legendre, P., Oksanen, J., Ter Braak, C.J.F., 2011. Testing the significance of canonical axes in redundancy analysis. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 2, 269–277. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2041-210X.2010.00078.x>.
- Lischka, S., Hagen, W., 2007. Seasonal lipid dynamics of the copepods *Pseudocalanus minutus* (Calanoida) and *Oithona similis* (Cyclopoida) in the Arctic Kongsfjorden (Svalbard). *Marine Biology* 150, 443–454. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00227-006-0359-4>.
- Litchman, E., Ohman, M.D., Kjørboe, T., 2013. Trait-based approaches to zooplankton communities. *Journal of Plankton Research* 35, 473–484. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbt019>.
- Lundesgaard, Ø., Sundfjord, A., Lind, S., Nilsen, F., Renner, A.H., 2022. Import of Atlantic Water and sea ice controls the ocean environment in the northern Barents Sea. *Ocean Science* 18, 1389–1418. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-18-1389-2022>.
- Maitner, B.S., Halbritter, A.H., Telford, R.J., Strydom, T., Chacon, J., Lamanna, C., Sloat, L.L., Kerkhoff, A.J., Messier, J., Rasmussen, N., Pomati, F., Merz, E., Vandvik, V., Enquist, B.J., 2023. Bootstrapping outperforms community-weighted approaches for estimating the shapes of phenotypic distributions. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 14, 2592–2610. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.14160>.
- Maps, F., Storozenko, P.P., Świeżewski, J., Ayata, S.-D., 2024. Automatic estimation of lipid content from *in situ* images of Arctic copepods using machine learning. *Journal of Plankton Research* 46, 41–47. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbad048>.
- Mariani, P., Andersen, K.H., Visser, A.W., Barton, A.D., Kjørboe, T., 2013. Control of plankton seasonal succession by adaptive grazing. *Limnology and Oceanography* 58, 173–184. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lno.2013.58.1.0173>.
- McGinty, N., Barton, A.D., Record, N.R., Finkel, Z.V., Irwin, A.J., 2018. Traits structure copepod niches in the North Atlantic and Southern Ocean. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 601, 109–126. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps12660>.
- Morris, M., Gust, G., Torres, J., 1985. Propulsion efficiency and cost of transport for copepods: a hydro-mechanical model of crustacean swimming. *Marine Biology* 86, 283–295. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00397515>.
- Nakken, O., 1998. Past, present and future exploitation and management of marine resources in the Barents Sea and adjacent areas. *Fisheries research* 37, 23–35. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-7836\(98\)00124-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-7836(98)00124-6).
- Niemi, A., Bluhm, B.A., Juul-Pedersen, T., Kohlbach, D., Reigstad, M., Søgaard, D.H., Amiraux, R., 2024. Ice algae contributions to the benthos during a time of sea ice change: a review of supply, coupling, and fate. *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 12, 1432761. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2024.1432761>.
- Oliveira, L.D.F.D., Bode-Dalby, M., Schukat, A., Auel, H., Hagen, W., 2022. Cascading effects of calanoid copepod functional groups on the biological carbon pump in the

- subtropical South Atlantic. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.920483>.
- Olsen, T., Stige, L.C., Dupont, N., Durant, J.M., Langangen, Ø., 2024. Repeated large declines in the Barents Sea capelin population are associated with different ecosystem conditions. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 81, 1584–1593. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsae101>.
- Oziel, L., Sirven, J., Gascard, J.C., 2016. The Barents Sea frontal zones and water masses variability (1980–2011). *Ocean Sci* 12, 169–184. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-12-169-2016>.
- Pedersen, T., Mikkelsen, N., Lindstrøm, U., Renaud, P.E., Nascimento, M.C., Blanchet, M.-A., Ellingsen, I.H., Jørgensen, L.L., Blanchet, H., 2021. Overexploitation, recovery, and warming of the Barents Sea ecosystem during 1950–2013. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8, 732637. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.732637>.
- Pinti, J., Jónasdóttir, S.H., Record, N.R., Visser, A.W., 2023. The global contribution of seasonally migrating copepods to the biological carbon pump. *Limnology and Oceanography* 68, 1147–1160. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.12335>.
- Polyakov, I.V., Ingvaldsen, R.B., Pnyushkov, A.V., Bhatt, U.S., Francis, J.A., Janout, M., Kwok, R., Skagseth, Ø., 2023. Fluctuating Atlantic inflows modulate Arctic atlantification. *Science* 381, 972–979. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adh5158>.
- Pomerleau, C., Sastri, A.R., Beisner, B.E., 2015. Evaluation of functional trait diversity for marine zooplankton communities in the Northeast subarctic Pacific Ocean. *Journal of Plankton Research* 37, 712–726. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbv045>.
- Oksanen, J. S. G., Blanchet F, Kindt R, Legendre P, Minchin P, O'hara R, Solyomos P, Stevens M, Szocs E, W. H., Barbour M, Bedward M, Bolker B, Borcard D, Carvalho G, Chirico M, De Caceres M, Durand S, Evangelista H, F. R., Friendly M, Furneaux B, Hannigan G, Hill M, Lahti L, Mcglinn D, Ouellette M, and Ribeiro Cunha E, S. T., Stier a, Ter Braak C, Weedon J (2022) vegan: Community Ecology Package. R package version 2.6-4 ed. doi: 10.32614/CRAN.package.vegan10.32614/CRAN.package.vegan.
- Postel L, F. H., Hagen W (2000) Biomass and abundance. In: A. Press (ed) In ICES Zooplankton Methodology Manual. pp. 83–192. doi: 10.1016/B978-012327645-2/50005-0.
- Prowe, A.E.F., Visser, A.W., Andersen, K.H., Chiba, S., Kjørboe, T., 2019. Biogeography of zooplankton feeding strategy. *Limnology and Oceanography* 64, 661–678. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.11067>.
- Ramondenc, S., Nöthig, E.M., Hufnagel, L., Bauerfeind, E., Busch, K., Knüppel, N., Kraft, A., Schröter, F., Seifert, M., Iversen, M.H., 2023. Effects of Atlantification and changing sea-ice dynamics on zooplankton community structure and carbon flux between 2000 and 2016 in the eastern Fram Strait. *Limnology and Oceanography* 68, S39–S53. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.12192>.
- Record, N.R., Ji, R., Maps, F., Varpe, Ø., Runge, J.A., Petrik, C.M., Johns, D., 2018. Copepod diapause and the biogeography of the marine lipid landscape. *Journal of Biogeography* 45, 2238–2251. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.13414>.
- Richardson, A.J., 2008. In hot water: zooplankton and climate change. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 65, 279–295. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsn028>.
- Sainmont, J., Andersen, K.H., Varpe, Ø., Visser, A.W., 2014. Capital versus income breeding in a seasonal environment. *The American Naturalist* 184, 466–476. <https://doi.org/10.1086/677926>.
- Sakshaug, E., Johnsen, G., Kovacs, K., 2009. Ecosystem Barents Sea. *Polar Biol* 34, 1253–1254 (2011). doi: 10.1007/s00300-011-0985-2.
- San Martin, E., Harris, R.P., Irigoien, X., 2006. Latitudinal variation in plankton size spectra in the Atlantic Ocean. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 53, 1560–1572. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr2.2006.05.006>.
- Sargent, J. (1978) Marine wax esters. *Science Progress* (1933-), 65, 437–458. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43423735>.
- Schmid, M.S., Maps, F., Fortier, L., 2018. Lipid load triggers migration to diapause in Arctic *Calanus* copepods—insights from underwater imaging. *Journal of Plankton Research* 40, 311–325. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fby012>.
- Scott, C.L., Kwasniewski, S., Falk-Petersen, S., Sargent, J.R., 2000. Lipids and life strategies of *Calanus finmarchicus*, *Calanus glacialis* and *Calanus hyperboreus* in late autumn, Kongsfjorden, Svalbard. *Polar Biology* 23, 510–516. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s003000000114>.
- Screen, J.A., Simmonds, I., 2010. The central role of diminishing sea ice in recent Arctic temperature amplification. *Nature* 464, 1334–1337. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature09051>.
- Sodrè, E.D.O., Bozelli, R.L., 2019. How planktonic microcrustaceans respond to environment and affect ecosystem: a functional trait perspective. *International Aquatic Research* 11, 207–223. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40071-019-0233-x>.
- Sundfjord, A., Assmann, K.M., Lundesgaard, Ø., Renner, A.H.H., Lind, S., Ingvaldsen, R. B., 2020. Suggested water mass definitions for the central and northern Barents Sea, and the adjacent Nansen Basin. The Nansen Legacy Report Series. <https://doi.org/10.7557/nlrs.5707>.
- Tang, Q., Yang, J., Sun, D., 2022. Functional diversity of copepod assemblages along a basin-scale latitudinal gradient in the North Pacific Ocean. *Ecological Indicators* 141, 109112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2022.109112>.
- Trudnowska, E., Lacour, L., Ardyna, M., Rogge, A., Irissou, J.O., Waite, A.M., Babin, M., Stemmann, L., 2021. Marine snow morphology illuminates the evolution of phytoplankton blooms and determines their subsequent vertical export. *Nature communications* 12, 2816. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-22994-4>.
- Våge, S., Basedow, S.L., Tande, K.S., Zhou, M., 2014. Physical structure of the Barents Sea Polar Front near Storbanken in August 2007. *Journal of Marine Systems* 130, 256–262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2011.11.019>.
- Varpe, Ø., Jørgensen, C., Tarling, G.A., Fiksen, Ø., 2009. The adaptive value of energy storage and capital breeding in seasonal environments. *Oikos* 118, 363–370. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0706.2008.17036.x>.
- Venello, T.A., Sastri, A.R., Galbraith, M.D., Dower, J.F., 2021. Zooplankton functional group responses to environmental drivers off the west coast of Vancouver Island, Canada. *Progress in Oceanography* 190, 102482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2020.102482>.
- Vilgrain, L., Maps, F., Picheral, M., Babin, M., Aubry, C., Irissou, J.O., Ayata, S.D., 2021. Trait-based approach using in situ copepod images reveals contrasting ecological patterns across an Arctic ice melt zone. *Limnology and Oceanography* 66, 1155–1167. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.11672>.
- Violle, C., Navas, M.-L., Vile, D., Kazakou, E., Fortunel, C., Hummel, I., Garnier, E., 2007. Let the concept of trait be functional! *Oikos* 116, 882–892. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0030-1299.2007.15559.x>.
- Visser, A.W., Brun, P., Chakraborty, S., Dencker, T.S., Van Denderen, P.D., Van Gemert, R., Van Someren Gréve, H., Heilmann, I., Holm, M.W., Jónasdóttir, S.H., Kenitz, K.M., Kjørboe, T., Lindegren, M., Mariani, P., Nielsen, L.T., Pancic, M., Payne, M., Pécuchet, L., Schnedler-Meyer, N.A., Thygesen, U.H., Törnroos, A., Andersen, K.H., 2020. Seasonal strategies in the world's oceans. *Progress in Oceanography* 189, 102466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2020.102466>.
- Visser, A.W., Fiksen, Ø., 2013. Optimal foraging in marine ecosystem models: selectivity, profitability and switching. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 473, 91–101. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps10079>.
- Vogt, R.J., Peres-Neto, P.R., Beisner, B.E., 2013. Using functional traits to investigate the determinants of crustacean zooplankton community structure. *Oikos* 122, 1700–1709. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0706.2013.00039.x>.
- Ward, B.A., Dutkiewicz, S., Jahn, O., Follows, M.J., 2012. A size-structured food-web model for the global ocean. *Limnology and Oceanography* 57, 1877–1891. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lno.2012.57.6.1877>.
- Wassmann, P., Kosobokova, K., Slagstad, D., Drinkwater, K., Hopcroft, R., Moore, S., Ellingsen, I., Nelson, R., Carmack, E., Popova, E., 2015. The contiguous domains of Arctic Ocean advection: Trails of life and death. *Progress in Oceanography* 139, 42–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2015.06.011>.
- Wassmann, P., Reigstad, M., Haug, T., Rudels, B., Carroll, M.L., Hop, H., Gabrielsen, G. W., Falk-Petersen, S., Denisenko, S.G., Arashkevich, E., Slagstad, D., Pavlova, O., 2006. Food webs and carbon flux in the Barents Sea. *Progress in Oceanography* 71, 232–287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2006.10.003>.
- Wold, A., Hop, H., Svendsen, C., Søreide, J.E., Assmann, K.M., Ormanczyk, M., Kwasniewski, S., 2023. Atlantification influences zooplankton communities seasonally in the northern Barents Sea and Arctic Ocean. *Progress in Oceanography* 219, 103133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2023.103133>.
- Zheng, Z., Fu, S., Li, Y., Ge, R., Chen, H., Ye, Z., Zhuang, Y., Liu, G., 2023. Functional groups and seasonal diversity of crustacean zooplankton in adjacent waters of Haizhou Bay, South Yellow Sea. *Journal of Oceanology and Limnology* 41, 1007–1023. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00343-022-1360-6>.